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THE USE OF ACTIVE METHODOLOGIES AS AN INNOVATIVE PROCESS IN TEACHER TRAINING

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ABSTRACT

This article aimed to analyze the contribution of active methodologies to teacher training and practice in the teaching-learning process at the EEEM CEI “Áttila de Almeida Miranda” school, seeking to explore new fields of knowledge and implement a bold teaching method to revive the constant pursuit of knowledge. Studying active methodologies refers to innovative practices capable of moving students from the traditional classroom environment to a place of decision-making, experimentation, and awareness of their practices. They can thus help students become autonomous and liberating individuals. Given this scenario, the school needs to redesign itself and adopt new teaching practices. In this context, it is necessary for teachers to be in constant training, acquiring knowledge and putting these new ways of constructing knowledge into practice. The objective of this study was to verify the contribution of active methodologies in teaching practice to the teaching-learning process of students at the EEEM CEI “Áttila de Almeida Miranda” school. Considering the results presented, it is clear that changes in the educational sector do not happen suddenly, but rather gradually. It is believed that more significant changes among the participants of this research are yet to come, and that the adoption of active methodologies in the routine practices of schools will increasingly contribute to pedagogical practices and the teaching-learning process.

Keywords: Teacher training. Active methodologies. Pedagogical practices.

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, education has become a formative and historical process for humankind. Educational methods can be considered technologies that facilitate the development of skills and modes of knowledge production (Pinto, 2015). Therefore, active learning methods are intellectual technologies. According to Pierre Lévy, "an intellectual technology almost always externalizes, objectifies, virtualizes a cognitive function, a mental activity" (Lévy, 1996).

The current educational landscape is undergoing constant transformations, especially in the field of communications and the expansion of information access, leading to a need for change in the traditional teaching paradigm. To meet the new social configurations, Education has been developing various types of active methods, such as active methodologies. Active Methodologies are understood as a strategic process of the teacher, in the organization of learning didactics (Pereira, 2012). In its application, the teacher should not only be the transmitter of objective content, but rather the one who teaches their students to think autonomously to the point of transforming their reality (Freire, 2015).

It is known that in their initial training, teachers do not possess all the knowledge necessary to meet all the demands of a classroom. This occurs because the educational landscape changes according to each reality, and therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to continue studying, undertaking ongoing training in order to relearn or reframe their daily practices, seeking to improve their knowledge and practices.

On the other hand, it is common to hear reports of dissatisfaction from teachers regarding technology; we observe many difficulties in the scientific process. There are complaints related to difficulties in often not being able to interact, even when in daily contact with students in the classroom who have and use technology. It is also noticeable that teachers are always feeling alone and insecure

in the task of promoting active methodologies in a certain way. Furthermore, there is a certain difficulty in obtaining support from specialized professionals.

METHODOLOGY

The methodological procedures will be explained here, detailing how the case study was conducted using a qualitative, descriptive approach. It will also clarify aspects of Bardin's (2011) content analysis, specifically regarding the modalities of interview, participant observation, and document analysis.

Research consists of a formal process for obtaining knowledge about a given reality, requiring reflection and scientific rigor. Although it seeks the truth, it is not limited to it. Therefore, the objective of scientific research is to seek, in an in-depth manner, answers to all the questions that are part of the investigation.

The research "locus" was the Áttila Almeida Miranda State High School, located at Av. Nossa Sra. da Consolação, 176 - Vila Rica, Cachoeiro de Itapemirim - ES, 29301-000, in the south of the state of Espírito Santo - Brazil.

Therefore, this study will seek to understand the complex phenomena, within the school context, relevant to the Áttila Almeida Miranda School in relation to pedagogical practices, active methodologies, the difficulties of including them, and their advantages.

It is up to education professionals to understand that both social interaction and experience involve both appropriate methods to be used and a good teacher-student relationship in order to achieve satisfactory learning and good joint practices. In this context, the social, economic, political, cultural, and technological transformations of recent decades have impacted people's lives, relationships, the job market, and the classroom.

ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION OF THE RESEARCH

This article aims to analyze and discuss the results of the research carried out at the EEEM CEI “Áttila de Almeida Miranda”, located in the municipality of Cachoeiro de Itapemirim, in the south of the State of Espírito Santo-Brazil.

The research was conducted as a “case study”, committed to a descriptive character in a qualitative approach, with information gathering in the field and document analysis, in order to better understand the pedagogical practices related to active methodologies in a high school.

The participants investigated in this study were: high school teachers, pedagogues, pedagogical coordinators and management.

Respondents will be identified by letters of the alphabet, followed by a number: (P.1 to P.10), (R.11 and R.12), (C. 13 and C.14) and (G.15).

The study was conducted with the purpose of analyzing the contribution of active methodologies in teacher training in the teaching-learning process of students at the EEEM CEI “Áttila de Almeida Miranda” school.

In order to achieve this purpose, a case study was carried out with a qualitative approach from the perspective of complexity. Data collection was carried out through interviews and document analysis of the pedagogical proposals of the school under investigation.

Question: How much teaching experience and activity have you had?

Chart: Categorization and coding of "Existing experience"

Performance (Experience of more than 5 years)	Performance level (Experience less than 5 years)
<p>P.1: "My initial training is in pedagogy, followed by a degree in Portuguese. I have a total of 17 years of experience working in education as a teacher";</p> <p>P.2: "I have a degree in Mathematics, with 14 years of experience"; P.3: "I have a degree in Physical Education and have been working for 7 years. I started here at this school."</p> <p>P.4: "I have a degree in Biology, both a teaching degree and a bachelor's degree, and 8 years of experience as a teacher."</p> <p>P.5: "I have a degree in Mathematics with a specialization in Physics, and I have been teaching for about 15 years."</p>	<p>P.6: "I have a degree in Chemistry, I started teaching only 3 years ago"</p> <p>P.8: "I have a degree in History, I have been a teacher for 4 years"</p> <p>P.10: "I studied pedagogy, I have been teaching for 3 years"</p> <p>R.11: "5 years of work and my initial training is in pedagogy"</p>
<p>P.7: "I have a degree in Pedagogy, I have done various specializations, and I have been working as a teacher for 7 years."</p> <p>P.9: "I have a degree in Pedagogy and 6 years of experience."</p> <p>R.12: "I have 18 years of experience in education and have a degree in Pedagogy."</p> <p>C.13: "I have a degree in Pedagogy and have been here for 12 years, and in education for 15 years."</p> <p>C.14: "I have a degree in Pedagogy and 8 years of experience."</p> <p>G.15: "I have a degree in Mathematics and have been in education for 16 years."</p>	

Source: Data compiled by the researcher, 2024

P- TEACHER

Many educational problems are primarily related to learning. As for the students, perhaps they become better because each one is in their specific area. In traditional teaching, based on the transmission of content, the student has a passive posture towards the teaching and learning processes, having the function of receiving and absorbing a huge amount of information presented by the teacher.

Here we observe that the service time of most of the interviewees (3 teachers) is less than 5 years, which leads us to their very recent initial training. The "being" a teacher is thus permeated by at least two important aspects: the historical and the discursive, constituting a profession of extreme importance, even though its beginning, already relating to the conflicts

faced by the "new" teacher, is quite challenging.

R- PEDAGOGUE

We observe that all Pedagogues have more than 5 years of experience; therefore, their training inevitably becomes much more comprehensive and complex. The professional side complements the personal side and vice-versa. The inseparability of the initial and ongoing training process of the Pedagogue from the formation of their personal and professional identity is evident. In this case, the relevance of exchanging experiences between "old" and "new" pedagogues is again apparent, because although academic training is fundamental, their experiences are unique and, therefore, offer the possibility of new knowledge for both.

C- COORDINATOR

We have no coordinators in our data with less than 5 years of experience, which gives us some comfort in discussing this coordinator's experience and teaching performance, since all have a fundamental characteristic for a good pedagogical coordinator: having a broad vision capable of considering various possible paths for conflict resolution. In short, we can say that the pedagogical coordinator needs this competence to act assertively in the school through open dialogue. Pedagogical coordination promotes the creation of bridges between members of the teaching staff through suggestions, considering the resources this will involve to transform teachers practices.

G- MANAGER

With the experience presented, the role of the manager in a school institution is fundamental, requiring not only knowledge and competence, but also the ability to dynamize and implement school policies aimed at achieving the proposed educational objectives. Traditionally, the manager was seen as an educator in the administration of the pedagogical project, as well as an administrator who followed the guidelines of higher bodies. This central

position in the school gives the manager significant power over the decisions made, representing order within the institution.

Question: "Do you have the resources to implement this new teaching model?"

Table: "Active Methodologies" and "Resources"

R.11	"Yes, today the school has the main tools, especially in relation to technological resources."
R.12	"Yes, we do."
C.13	"We lack a little time to execute everything that is proposed, but the school does have the necessary resources."
C.14	"Yes, for all the active methodologies already proposed, there has never been a lack of any type of resource."
G.15	"The school today has a good internet system, we have televisions, data projectors and other equipment, what's lacking is time to be able to use everything."

Source: Data compiled by the researcher, 2024

The coordinators and managers show interest and affirm that they have several projects underway. Therefore, the urgent need to promote, in initial teacher training, a balanced approach that encompasses both content mastery of the respective subject areas – traditionally known as "disciplines" – and mastery of knowledge specific to the teaching profession, guided by principles and values that extend beyond the restricted school environment, becomes apparent.

The participants' statements reveal that they do not encounter difficulties in using new technologies, but they point to "time" as the main obstacle to their use. In this context, "deifying or demonizing technology, or the unconventional in pedagogical practices, is a highly negative and dangerous way of thinking wrongly, because one cannot do without technology, nor can one allow oneself to be enslaved by it; balance and common sense are necessary in everything. Therefore, using technology in favor of education is intelligent, but one cannot expect it to be able to overcome cognitive obstacles. Thus, once again, the reflective praxis of the teacher in the execution of their planning can overcome factors such as

"lack of time" in carrying out activities."

Question: What changes were necessary to incorporate active learning methodologies into the school curriculum?

Table: "Incorporation of active learning methodologies into documents" and codification

G.15: It was necessary to adapt and make the curriculum more flexible so that pedagogical practices could be developed. A "rigid" curriculum without the necessary adaptations does not provide the basis for the application of active methodologies, as it does not allow for individual, collaborative, and guided learning paths, which need to be developed to meet needs and Learning, combining theory and practice.

Source: Data compiled by the researcher, 2024

In this context, choosing a curriculum goes beyond simply assembling disciplinary content for good professional training. Because choosing content that is not only specific to professional training, but also attractive and that sparks collective interest, is crucial; without this, knowledge would be restricted.

Thus, the teacher, through the practice of active methodologies, encourages students to take a leading role, contributing to direct, participatory, and reflective development at all stages of the process, experimenting, designing, and creating, with the teacher's guidance.

Traditional methods, which prioritize the transmission of information by teachers, made sense when access to information was difficult. With the Internet and the open dissemination of many courses and materials, we can learn anywhere, anytime, and with many different people. This is complex, necessary, and a little daunting, because we don't have successful previous models for learning flexibly in a highly connected society. (Almeida & Valente, 2012). What technology brings today is the integration of all spaces and times. Teaching and learning happens in a symbiotic, profound, constant interconnection between what we call the physical world and the digital world. They are not two worlds or spaces, but an extended space, an expanded classroom, that constantly

blends and hybridizes.

Teacher training for different levels of basic education is permeated by recurring issues in debates and research in Brazil. Although there is a legal framework that regulates the subject, significant changes in the process are generally not effective, due to factors such as high turnover and discontinuity of public policies for teacher training; a mismatch between the profile of teacher trainers and that expected of graduates from undergraduate teacher education programs; the absence of policies for monitoring and evaluating undergraduate teacher education curricula; and also due to recent issues arising from the new demands of contemporary society.

Among other aspects, the questions raised and those that emerge are driven both by "the need to train good teachers for each classroom in each school, and by the challenge of offering training processes relevant to a changing world."

It is known that for a school to function well and be successful, it is essential to first define its line of work. Numerous difficulties arise in the school context that can be addressed through the meaning of collective actions, discussed politically and systematized, thus revealing the school's identity through its Political-Pedagogical Project.

However, it is also known that there are challenges that need to be overcome in this construction and definition, as there are approaches that require reflection so that the school can achieve its greater objective, which is to offer quality education. These approaches are geared towards democratic management, the relationship with the community, the self-determination of the school (evidently without violating national guidelines and laws), the organization of its curriculum for meaningful teaching and learning accessible to all, and also the appreciation of its professionals as individuals responsible for this quality within the school.

The document needs to reflect the evolution of knowledge. Regarding this aspect, Veiga

(2003, pp. 11-12) reveals that: “the pedagogical project is, therefore, a specific product that reflects the reality of the school situated in a broader context that influences it and that can be influenced by it”. Veiga (2003) further states that: [...] “the project is a clarifying instrument of the school's educational action in its entirety”. Thus, it needs to be seen as an important step in the pursuit of improving teaching and school practices.

The Constitution establishes the following as basic principles of education: pluralism of ideas and pedagogical conceptions, and democratic management of public education. These principles can be considered as constitutional foundations of school autonomy (Brazil, 1988).

In the teachers' statements, the importance of curriculum adaptation and flexibility for the development of pedagogical practices is evident. A "rigid" curriculum without the necessary adaptations does not provide support for the application of active methodologies, as it does not allow for the individual, collaborative, and guidance-based learning paths that need to be developed to meet the needs and expectations of learning, combining theory and practice.

In turn, the pedagogical projects developed by schools should favor an innovative principle, reconciling "in the curricular organization, space, times, and projects that balance personal and collaborative communication, face-to-face and online, and that, under the guidance of a teacher, lead us to a higher level of synthesis of new skills" (Bacich & Moran, 2018, p.9).

In this context, choosing a curriculum goes beyond simply assembling disciplinary content for good professional training. It's about selecting content that is not only specific to professional training but also attractive and engaging for the group; without this, knowledge remains limited.

CONCLUSION

This article aims to highlight the use of active methodologies as an innovative process in teacher training. It examines how teacher

training has been fostered to promote blended learning. This work has shown that active methodologies take on a differentiated and adaptable character depending on the target audience, the course, and the pedagogical proposal in which they are implemented. Through the collected responses and bibliographic research, it is evident that they can be a reality that addresses multiple aspects: cognitive, emotional, and pedagogical, in what they propose, provided that the individuals involved in their application understand their philosophy and find adequate conditions for their development, encompassing both human and structural factors.

Participants working in basic education indicated the relevance of blended learning as a differentiating factor in their professional attitudes, attributing to it new ways of teaching, seeking to consolidate the identity and self-esteem of the educator. Some stated that the blended learning modality requires epistemological ruptures in school planning. Other contributions involve a differentiated perspective on the interfaces and practices developed in the classroom, which reinforces the scientific basis of teacher training.

This profession is based on science and linked to the inseparability of theory and practice, grounding praxis. These premises allow teachers to be reflective designers of problem situations. Thus, in contemporary times, teaching emphasizes the importance of research and an investigative spirit in the classroom, continuously building and rebuilding scientific knowledge in the pedagogical and technological areas to encourage the use of active methodologies and hybrid models in basic and higher education. Finally, notwithstanding the time limitations of a master's level scientific investigation, there is a need to implement hybrid education, aiming at the development of theoretical-scientific attitudes and theoretical-practical training that enhance the teaching profession in Brazil.

The administrative dimension will define joint actions with the participation of everyone, aiming to build and conduct its plans, programs,

and projects, so that it can also contribute to the teaching and learning process. The political-pedagogical project is a document with intentional action, with a commitment defined collectively. Therefore, the pedagogical project is also a political project, as it is directly linked to social and political commitment, simultaneously, with interests that are real and collective for the majority of the population. It has a political aspect given the school's commitment as a space for the formation of the individual for a specific type of society. And it is pedagogical because it defines and organizes educational actions, as well as the characteristics necessary for schools to fulfill their established goals that are necessary for teaching and learning.

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